

Magnetic and Magnetocaloric properties of $\text{Dy}_6\text{Ni}_2\text{Si}_3$ compound

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Abstract

Systematic investigations were carried out on the magnetic and magnetocaloric properties of arc melted $\text{Dy}_6\text{Ni}_2\text{Si}_3$ compound. The polycrystalline compound shows two ferromagnetic (FM) transitions at $T_1 = 44$ K and $T_2 = 72$ K respectively (Fig. 1). A slight spin reorientation like behavior is observed below T_1 around $T = 26$ K. The isothermal magnetization curve for $T = 2$ K reveals the presence spin reorientation at a critical field of 5 T. The magnetic entropy change (ΔS_m) computed from the isothermal magnetization data shows a maximum of 16.3 J/kg.K at 72 K for 9 T. Also, the presence of two magnetic transitions at $T_1 = 44$ K and $T_2 = 72$ K induces a table like magnetocaloric effect in a wide temperature range with a refrigerant capacity of 600 J/kg for a field change of 9 T. It also exhibits considerable negative magnetoresistance of 10% in 9 T at 2 K. Hence the magnetic properties observed for $\text{Dy}_6\text{Ni}_2\text{Si}_3$ are interesting for low temperature magnetic refrigeration. The detailed discussion on the magnetic properties will be presented in the symposium.

Keywords: Magnetocaloric effect, Spin reorientation, Magnetoresistance

Fig. 1. Temperature dependence of ZFC and FC magnetizations at $H = 100$ Oe